

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF COOLING DEGREE DAYS FOR FARM STRUCTURES ENERGY MANAGEMENT IN OKITIPUPA ONDO STATE NIGERIA

Adekunle A. ALLI*, Patrick O. DICKSON, Hakeem L. LADAPO, Adefemi S. OJO, and Ayodele S. OLADIPO

Department of Agricultural & Bio-environmental Engineering, Yaba College of Technology, Yaba Lagos

* Corresponding Author: adekunle.alli@yabatech.edu.ng

Abstract

Cooling or heating degree days can be best used to estimate energy use in buildings or farm structures. The data used for this study were obtained from the archive of National Aeronautics and Space Administration on monthly and annual bases from 1981 to 2024. The study area is Okitipupa with latitude 6.50 N and longitude 4.77 E. The temperature of 65 °F was used as a reference for being considered moderate. The MS Excel was used to analyse monthly data for descriptive statistics and forecasting. The findings revealed that energy use of farm structures is based on the purpose in which the structure is meant to serve, and the results for CDD at 18.33 °C shows that March has the highest mean daily temperatures of 27.08 °C. The forecast for annual CDD at 18.33 °C to 2050 recorded R squared of 0.51. The objective of the study is to assess the energy use of farm structures.

Keywords:

Celsius,
Fahrenheit,
Energy,
Degree Day,
Farm Structures

1. INTRODUCTION

Attention must be paid to the energy demand of farm structures or buildings as well as that of the residential since weather plays significant roles in determining the durability and efficiency of our buildings. Farm structures are classified based on the materials used for construction, and the purpose in which the structure is meant to serve. Cooling or heating degree days can be best used to estimate energy use in buildings or farm structures. Degree days are the difference between the mean daily temperature and the temperature of 65 °F (18.33 °C). On a cooling degree day, 65 °F is less than the mean daily temperature while it is heating if it is greater.

It is essential that the regulation of temperature is needed to enhance the potential of the agricultural storage facilities depending on the types of crops or fruits [1]. Livestock Health and Productivity basically depend on the ability to manage heat stress and ensure enhancement of the ventilation and cooling system in order to maintain animal comfort. The high cooling degree days values lead to heat stress in livestock which invariably affect their health, productivity, and mortality rates. The trend of Cooling degree days has been on the increase in Kano state Nigeria while on the decrease in Bamakko Mali [2].

The global rise in the temperature and sea level as a result of twain factors of climate change and global warming have significant impacts on the energy required for farm structures [3]. Among few researchers who have worked on the cooling degree days both nationally and internationally, none has considered farm structures. [4] worked on the trend and variations of cooling degree days in West Africa with a view to comparing the trend patterns. Also, [2] used global climate model data to look at the future cooling demand for cities in Africa. [5] studied cooling degree hour for determining energy demand across several cities in Nigeria.

It is crystal clear that the effort to keep the global mean temperature at 1.5 °C is unattainable as it is already tending towards 2.0 °C due to global warming [6-7]. The findings show that months of March for cooling degree days have the highest mean cooling degree days for the two temperature bases understudy. Meanwhile, the objective of this study is to assess the energy use of farm structures in the study area.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The study area is Okitipupa in Okitipupa Local Government of Ondo State Nigeria with latitude 6.50 N and longitude 4.77 E respectively with an elevation of 33 m. Okitipupa has a tropical climate with significant rainfall throughout the year with annual rainfall of 2578 mm. It has an average daily temperature of 25.8°C with highest relative humidity of about 90 % in the months of July to September [8].

2.2 Data Acquisition

The data used for this study were obtained from the archive of National Aeronautics and Space Administration (<https://www.power.larc.nasa.gov/data-access-viewer/>) on monthly and annual basis from 1981 to 2024 (43 years), which covered temperatures above 10 °C and 18.33 °C.

2.3 Statistical Tools and Calculations

MS Excel was used to analyse monthly data for descriptive statistics and forecasting.

2.3.1 Calculations

The Cooling Degree Days or Heating Degree Days is calculated according to [13] using Equation (1)

$$\frac{T_2 + T_1}{2} = T_m \tag{1}$$

where

T₂---high daily temperature

T₁----low daily temperature

T_m----mean daily temperature

65 °F (18.33 °C) is a reference temperature considered to be moderate.

If T_m is lesser than 65 °F is called Heating degree days, and it is cooling degree day if greater.

Equation (2) is used to convert Fahrenheit to Celsius or vice versa.

$$F = 1.8 C + 32 \tag{2}$$

where F is Fahrenheit and C is Celsius

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

Tables 1 and 2 show the descriptive statistics of the cooling degree days for temperatures 10°C and 18.33°C, with the highest mean monthly cooling degree days of 272.27°C and 839.57°C for base temperatures of 10°C and 18.33 °C, respectively, in the month of March. The base temperature of 10°C recorded a negative kurtosis value in October, while the base temperature of 18.33°C recorded negative kurtosis values in July, September, and October.

Table 1. Monthly Cooling Degree Days of Base Temperature 10°C

STATISTICS	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC
Mean	208.84	233.31	272.27	257.95	248.56	216.8 9	204.4 8	200.8 5	206.12	227.99	233.50	212.42
Standard Deviation	39.88	23.37	13.97	11.60	12.70	9.37	14.61	14.11	11.20	12.78	17.05	26.66
Kurtosis	0.62	1.23	0.87	0.47	0.12	1.36	-0.22	1.65	-0.23	-0.58	0.03	0.06
Skewness	-0.82	-1.06	-0.22	0.51	0.38	0.31	0.14	-0.40	0.01	-0.17	-0.94	-0.53
Minimum	92.95	164.74	235.93	230.20	225.53	193.5 3	175.9 9	161.3 9	186.02	199.51	192.38	143.48
Maximum	273.74	265.84	305.54	287.19	279.38	245.9 4	238.5 5	234.6 6	232.33	253.75	258.79	255.94

Table 2. Cooling Degree Days of Base Temperature 18.33°C

Statistics	Jan	Feb	Mar	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
Mean	776.14	750.29	839.57	806.94	815.85	765.89	771.78	768.15	755.11	795.29	782.50	779.71
Standard Deviation	39.88	26.05	13.97	11.60	12.70	9.37	14.61	14.10	11.20	12.78	17.05	26.66
Kurtosis	0.62	0.97	0.87	0.47	0.12	1.36	-0.22	1.65	-0.23	-0.58	0.03	0.06
Skewness	-0.82	-0.76	0.22	0.51	0.38	0.31	0.14	-0.40	0.01	-0.17	-0.94	-0.53
Minimum	660.25	677.14	803.23	779.19	792.82	742.53	743.29	728.68	735.02	766.81	741.38	710.78
Maximum	841.04	796.54	872.84	836.19	846.8	794.94	805.85	801.96	781.31	821.05	807.79	823.24

Table 3 shows the temperature ranges for various livestock and farm structures. The temperature range for the green house depends on the types of crops or vegetables to be grown.

Table 3. Temperature Ranges of Animal and Farm Structures

Animal/ Farm Structures	Temperature Range in °C
Cattle	38- 39
Sheep	38.3 - 39.3
Goat	38.5 - 39.7
Pig	38.7 - 39.8
Horses	37.2 - 38.2
Chicken (day light)	40.6 - 43.0
Calf Barns	21 - 27
Dairy Barns	16 - 24
Poultry	18 - 24
Green House	16 - 27

Source: [9]

Figure 1 shows the daily mean cooling degree days in which the month of March recorded the highest value of 27.08 °C, and followed by Month of April with value of 26.90 °C. Month of August recorded the lowest value of 24.78 °C. The fourth order polynomial shows R squared of 0.93.

Figure 1. Daily Mean Cooling Degree Days

Figures 2 and 3 show the forecast graphs of cooling degree days for temperature base at 10 °C and 18.33 ° C respectively on annual basis to 2050. The polynomial fourth order of R² of 0.51 and 0.50 are recorded for cooling degree days for temperature bases at 10 °C and 18.33 ° C respectively.

Figure 2. Forecast of Cooling Degree Days above base temperature of 10°C

Figure 3. Forecast of Cooling Degree Days above base temperature of 18.33°C

3.2 Discussions

Okitipupa is expected to experience a continued increase in cooling degree days, based on the forecast results shown in Figures 2 and 3. This implies that more energy will be required for humans, livestock, and farm storage facilities. This is consistent with the findings of [3], which indicate that temperature is on an upward trend.

Figure 1 indicates that Okitipupa is a relatively warm town, and with a population growth rate of 2.7 % between 2006 and 2022 and a population density of 449.5 persons per km² [10], the demand for energy will certainly increase. Okitipupa is a growing city in terms of both population and development, and population growth significantly increases cooling degree days (CDDs), especially in warmer regions, which invariably leads to higher energy consumption for cooling. This situation is further exacerbated by the effects of global warming, which raise temperatures and consequently increase the demand for cooling.

As cooling degree days (CDDs) increase, the demand for energy used for cooling also rises. This occurs because higher outdoor temperatures require more energy to maintain comfortable indoor environments.

During periods of peak CDDs, the energy supply can become strained, potentially leading to higher energy prices and increased greenhouse gas emissions. This pressure on the energy system may only be reduced if renewable energy sources are sufficiently integrated into the supply mix.

Cooling degree days significantly influence energy demand in the context of climate change, increased energy consumption, and energy management. The higher the CDD values, the more energy is required for cooling. As such, CDDs serve as a vital metric for utility companies to forecast and manage energy demand effectively.

In the design of a farmhouse or storage structure, the temperature requirements of the specific animals or stored contents must be taken into consideration. For example, in the month of March, the cooling degree days value is 27.08 °C, and the normal body temperature range for goats is 38.5 – 39.7 °C. This implies that to maintain comfort, goats require an ambient temperature of approximately 11.42 – 12.62 °C. In building a goat pen, adequate provision must be made for a heating system. Likewise, poultry has a temperature range of 18 – 24°C, and analyzing it with cooling degree days for March (27.08°C), it shows that a cooling system is required for poultry houses. Meanwhile, heating and cooling systems are required for chicken (daylight) housing and grain storage facility with the temperature range of 40.6 – 43.0°C and 10 – 15°C, respectively. However, the cooling system for a grain storage facility must not contain moisture in order not to encourage microbial activities that are capable of causing spoilage. Therefore, with the rising in global temperature, understanding cooling degree days can help stakeholders make informed decisions for sustainable energy use and management.

This study contributes to knowledge as follows:

- i. It enhances knowledge on climate action.
- ii. It can enable policy makers to make climate-informed decision in farm energy management.
- iii. It aids understanding of Cooling Degree days pattern.
- iv. It helps in Energy consumption forecasting.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

[11] reported that for every CDD value increase, electricity consumption rises by approximately 0.04%. The relationship between CDD and energy demand is also influenced by factors like climate change, population growth, and urbanization, making CDD a crucial metric for energy management and planning [12].

It has shown that major economic losses in livestock production and farm produce storage facilities are caused by both heat stress and cold. Therefore, in order to forestall these losses, apt attention must be given to design consideration of farm structures. High cooling degree days values lead to heat stress in livestock which in return affect their health, productivity, and mortality rates.

Heat stress also leads to spoilage due to the increase in the microbial activities in the storage facilities. If the temperature is not properly controlled, it will build up moisture in the space of storage facilities which invariably enhance the microbial activities that lead to spoilage and decrease shelf life of the farm.

5.2 Recommendation

In order to achieve effective heat stress management, and considering the fact that cooling degree days in Okitipupa are projected to continue increasing, leading to higher energy demand, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. Farm structures especially for livestock housing require additional ventilation and cooling systems to mitigate heat stress and maintain animal comfort.
- ii. More alternative energies must be exploited since study has supported it that every rise in cooling degree day will attract about 0.04% electricity consumption.
- iii. Farm structures may require shading and cooling systems to protect crops and livestock from extreme temperatures.
- iv. Proper insulation and ventilation in farm structures can help regulate temperatures and reduce heat stress.

REFERENCES

- [1] Priyanka, R., Chaudhay, X., Guddadarangav, J., Jayaprakasha, B., and Managouda, S (2016). Influence of Storage Temperature and Low-temperature Conditioning on the level of Health-Promoting Compounds in Rio Red Grape. *Journal of Food Science and Nutrition*. 5 (3): 545- 553.
- [2] Dicko, K., Umaru, E. T., Sanogo, S., Okhimamhe, A. A., and Loewner, R (2024). A Trend Analysis of Changes in Cooling Degree Days in West Africa under Global Warming. *Journal of Atmosphere*, 15 (11): 1376- 1382
- [3] Sigmond, M., Fyfe, J. C., Sachko, O.A., and Swart, N. C. (2020). Ongoing AMOC and Related Sea Level and Temperature Changes after Achieving the Paris Target. *Journal of Nature Climate Change*. 10 (7): 1- 6.
- [4] Akara, G. K., Hingray, B., Diawara, A., and Diedhiou, A (2021). Effect of weather on monthly Electricity Consumption in three Coastal Cities in West Africa. *Journal of AIMS Energy*,9: 446–464.
- [5] Awolola, O. O., and Olorunmaiye, J. A (2020). Cooling Degree Days for Estimating Energy Consumption in Air Conditioning Systems in Nigeria. *Journal of Clean Energy Technologies*, 8: 5–10.
- [6] Miranda, N. D., Lizana, J., Sparrow, S. N., Zachau-Walker, M., Watson, P. A., Wallom, D. C., Khosla, R., and McCulloch, M (2023). Change in Cooling Degree Days with Global Mean Temperature Rise Increasing from 1.5 °C to 2. 0 °C. *Journal of Nature Sustainability* .6: 1326–1330.
- [7] Raul, C., Roberto, B., Carmen, S., Ricardo, B., Loanna, K., Eleftheria, P., Nikolaos, S., Dusana, D., Joao, P, Jozsef, K, Tareq, A., and Pedro, P (2021). Cooling Degree Models and Future Energy Demand in the Residential Sector. A Case Study of Seven- Country. *Journal of Sustainability*, 13 (5): 2987- 2992.
- [8] Weather Atlas. www.weather-atlas.com/en/Nigeria/Okitipupa-Climate updated July 8, 2024.
- [9] Merck and Coy Rahway (2016). www.msdrvvetmanual.com/multimedia/table/normal-rectal-temperature-range. Retrieved on the 10th June, 2025.

- [10] CityPopulation.de. (2024). *Okitipupa Local Government Area (Ondo, Nigeria) — Population statistics, charts and map*. Retrieved from https://www.citypopulation.de/en/nigeria/admin/ondo/NGA029014__okitipupa/ Retrieved on the 10th June, 2025.
- [11] Gunnar, S. K., Steffen, K., Zbignems, K., Terje, B., and Nathan, R (2010). Electricity Demand in a Changing Climate. *Journal of Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies*, 15 (8): 877- 897. doi.10.1007/s11027-010.9246.
- [12] Falchetta, G., and Mistry, M. N (2021). The role of residential air circulation and cooling Demand for Electrification Planning: Implications of Climate Change in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Energy Economics*. 99: 105- 1
- [13] Al-Hadhrani, L.M (2013). Comprehensive review of cooling and heating degree days characteristics over Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 27: 305-314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2013.04.034>.